

Angelo Leogrande^{1*}

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Gross Domestic Expenditure on R&D Funded from Abroad as a Percentage of GDP

The variable "GERD financed by abroad, % GDP" represents the total expenditure on research and development (R&D) of a country funded by foreign sources, expressed as a percentage of the gross domestic product (GDP). This measure includes foreign investments from foreign governments, international organizations, and multinational corporations, reflecting international cooperation and the country's ability to attract foreign funds for R&D. A high percentage indicates a high integration into the global research and development landscape, significantly contributing to the national economy. This variable is used to evaluate innovation policies, economic analyses, and international benchmarking, providing a clear view of the impact of foreign funding on a country's R&D. The data is available for the period from 2013 to 2022.

Gross Domestic Expenditure on R&D Funded from Abroad as a Percentage of GDP in 2022. The analysis of the data relating to gross domestic expenditure on research and development (GERD) funded from abroad as a percentage of GDP for the year 2022 reveals a complex and varied picture of R&D funding dynamics on a global level. This indicator is crucial to understanding the integration of countries into international research networks and their ability to attract foreign funds for innovation and technological development. Observing the data, it emerges that countries vary significantly in the percentage of GERD funded from abroad. Some countries show a significant dependence on foreign funding, while others receive negligible or no amounts. Countries like Austria (91.2%), Belgium (80.2%), Finland (74.9%), and countries like Czechia, Iceland, and Israel, with 100% foreign funding, demonstrate a strong capacity to attract foreign investments for research, indicating a strategy focused on attracting external investments for their research. On the other hand, countries like Germany (40.5%) and France (30.6%) have a robust internal research infrastructure but also significantly benefit from foreign funding, reflecting good integration into global research networks. Italy, with 24.2%, and other countries like Poland (16.1%) and Portugal (18.2%) show a fair ability to attract foreign funds. However, some countries like Argentina (8.2%), Mali (25.3%), and Burkina Faso (5.1%) have low percentages of foreign funding, indicating that most research is likely funded domestically. Countries like Albania, Azerbaijan, Ghana, and Kenya receive no foreign funding for R&D, which could indicate a poor ability to attract international funds or a lack of adequate research infrastructure. At a regional level, Europe shows a strong dependence on foreign funding, likely thanks to cooperative programs such as Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe. Canada, with 26.6% GERD financed from abroad, indicates a significant presence of foreign funding, while Asia presents a varied situation, with countries like China (1.5%) and South Korea (2%) having low percentages of foreign funding, likely reflecting a robust internal funding capacity. Latin American countries generally show low percentages of foreign funding, except for Argentina with 8.2%. The ability to attract foreign funding for R&D has various economic and political implications. Countries with high percentages of foreign funding can benefit from advanced technologies, know-how, and collaborations that might not be available domestically. However, a strong dependence on foreign funds can also pose risks, such as vulnerability to changes in international donor policies or global

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.cultore@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

economic fluctuations. Conversely, countries with low levels of foreign funding might have greater autonomy in determining their research priorities but may also be limited in the resources available to develop research and innovation capacities. For such countries, policies aimed at improving attractiveness for foreign R&D investments, such as tax incentives or the creation of special economic zones for technology, could be effective strategies. In summary, the data on GERD financed from abroad as a percentage of GDP reveals significant variability among countries, with some demonstrating a notable capacity to attract foreign funds and others being more autonomous or less able to do so. This diversity reflects not only differences in research infrastructure and national policies but also the position of each country in the global research and development landscape. Nations with high foreign funding can leverage collaborations and advanced technologies but must also manage the potential risks associated with dependence on foreign funds.

Analysis of Gross Domestic Expenditure on R&D Funded from Abroad as a Percentage of GDP from 2013 to 2022. The analysis of data relating to research and development (R&D) expenditure funded from abroad as a percentage of GDP between 2013 and 2022 shows significant variations both in absolute and percentage terms, reflecting different economic, political, and social dynamics across various countries. Among the countries that have seen the largest percentage increases in foreign-funded R&D expenditure, Malaysia stands out with an impressive increase of 3166.67%, rising from 0.30% to 9.80%. This increase can be attributed to a series of policies aimed at encouraging foreign investments and improving research infrastructure. Similarly, Argentina recorded an 811.11% increase, growing from 0.90% to 8.20%. Developed countries like Finland and Germany also saw significant increases of 634.31% and 575%, respectively, reflecting increasing integration into international research networks and greater attraction of foreign funds. Iceland recorded a 541.03% increase, reaching 100% of R&D expenditure funded from abroad. This figure suggests complete dependence on foreign funding, which could be indicative of a national strategy to leverage international resources for research. Other European countries like Slovenia, Belgium, and Bulgaria saw increases of 331.19%, 326.60%, and 324.62%, respectively, highlighting strong growth in their ability to attract foreign investments. Czechia achieved a 321.94% increase, with 100% of its R&D funded from abroad, while Austria saw a 276.86% increase, reaching 91.20%. These figures suggest a high degree of international collaboration and strong integration into European research projects. Other countries like Portugal and Switzerland recorded increases of 264% and 254.35%, respectively, indicating a strengthening of relationships with international funders. On the other hand, numerous countries have seen a significant reduction in the percentage of R&D funded from abroad. Burkina Faso recorded a drastic 94.50% decline, dropping from 92.70% to 5.10%. This decline could be due to political or economic instability, making the country less attractive for foreign investments. Other countries like Mozambique (-78.40%), Ethiopia (-80.47%), and Senegal (-86.72%) saw significant reductions, suggesting a decrease in interest or capacity to attract foreign funding. Panama recorded an 88.57% decline, while El Salvador saw a 90.86% decrease, both likely reflecting changes in national policies or economic stability. Countries like the Philippines (-92.19%) and Burkina Faso (-94.50%) saw drastic reductions, which could indicate disinvestment by international funders or a redirection of resources to other priorities. The variations in foreign funding for R&D reflect different national strategies and economic contexts. Significant increases in countries like Malaysia and Argentina can be interpreted as successes in policies to attract foreign investments and develop research infrastructure. In developed countries, the increase in foreign funding may indicate a growing integration into global research networks and an ability to leverage international resources to boost their innovation capacities. On the other hand, significant declines in countries like Burkina Faso, Mozambique, and Senegal suggest that these countries may face significant challenges in attracting and retaining foreign R&D investments. These declines may be due to factors such as political instability, changes in national priorities, or increasing competition from other countries. In summary, the data shows a dynamic landscape of R&D expenditure funded from abroad between 2013 and 2022. While some countries have made significant progress in attracting foreign funding,

others have seen a substantial decline, reflecting diverse economic, political, and strategic conditions worldwide. For countries that have seen an increase, strengthening international collaborations and further developing research infrastructure could continue to support this growth. For countries that have seen a decline, a reconsideration of policies and strategies to attract foreign investments, along with efforts to improve economic stability and attractiveness, might be necessary.

Economic Policies to Increase the Value of Foreign-Funded R&D Investments. Increasing the value of foreign-funded research and development (R&D) investments as a percentage of GDP requires a set of strategic economic policies aimed at creating a favorable environment for foreign investments. Governments can offer tax credits and exemptions to companies that invest in R&D, making these investments more financially attractive. Additionally, investing in the creation and enhancement of high-quality research centers equipped with the latest technologies and facilities can attract foreign investments. Developing technology parks and special economic zones with specific incentives for R&D activities can provide the ideal environment for foreign investors. Establishing bilateral and multilateral agreements with other countries to promote R&D cooperation can increase the flow of foreign investments, while active participation in international research programs can enhance the country's visibility and attractiveness for foreign R&D investments. Investing in education, particularly in STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) fields, to ensure a skilled workforce ready to participate in R&D projects is essential, as well as promoting collaborations between universities and industries to create a talent pipeline for companies operating in R&D. Strengthening intellectual property laws to protect the innovations and patents of foreign companies increases confidence in investments, and reducing bureaucracy and simplifying procedures for starting and managing R&D activities can make the country more attractive to foreign investors. Offering grants and direct funding to companies investing in R&D can reduce financial risk and incentivize foreign investments, while creating venture capital funds specifically dedicated to R&D projects can attract foreign investments, especially in emerging technology sectors. Launching international promotion campaigns to highlight the opportunities for R&D investments in the country can draw the attention of potential foreign investors, and participating in international fairs and industry events to present R&D opportunities and meet potential investors is another important step. Creating incubators and accelerators for start-ups operating in the R&D field can stimulate innovation and attract foreign investments, while promoting open innovation policies that encourage collaborations between large companies and start-ups can foster an innovative ecosystem attractive to foreign investments. Implementing a combination of these policies can significantly increase the value of foreign-funded R&D investments as a percentage of GDP. The key is to create an environment that not only attracts foreign investments but retains them through solid infrastructure, adequate incentives, intellectual property protection, and a skilled workforce. Through these initiatives, countries can improve their global competitiveness and promote sustainable long-term innovation.

Conclusions. The value of foreign-funded research and development expenditure grew on average by 17.08% between 2013 and 2022, rising from an amount of 20.23 to a value of 23.69 units. Among the countries that have recorded significant growth in the level of foreign-funded R&D expenditure between 2013 and 2022 are Malaysia with a value of +3166.67%, Argentina with +811.11%, Finland with +634.31%, Germany with +575%, and South Korea with +566.67%. However, some countries have experienced a significant reduction in the value of foreign-funded R&D investment as a percentage of GDP, namely Chile with -86.89%, Panama with -88.57%, El Salvador with -90.86%, the Philippines with -92.19%, and Burkina Faso with -94.50%.

Link: <https://prosperitydata360.worldbank.org/en/indicator/WIPO+GII+63>

Rank	Country	2022	Rank	Country	2022
1	Czechia	100	37	South Africa	14,6
2	Iceland	100	38	Belarus	13,7
3	Israel	100	39	Uganda	13
4	Austria	91,2	40	Malaysia	9,8
5	Belgium	80,2	41	Ethiopia	9,1
6	Finland	74,9	42	Panama	8,8
7	Bulgaria	55,2	43	Romania	8,8
8	Lithuania	52,5	44	Malta	8,6
9	Sweden	51,7	45	Argentina	8,2
10	Slovenia	47	46	Luxembourg	7,9
11	Croatia	45,9	47	Senegal	7,9
12	United Kingdom	42,7	48	Montenegro	6,8
13	Latvia	42,5	49	Hong Kong SAR, China	5,5
14	Germany	40,5	50	Burkina Faso	5,1
15	Netherlands	39,2	51	Uruguay	5
16	Estonia	37,5	52	Tunisia	4,3
17	Greece	37,3	53	Turkiye	3,8
18	Hungary	33,4	54	Paraguay	3,5
19	Switzerland	32,6	55	Russian Federation	3,3
20	France	30,6	56	Chile	3,2
21	Norway	30,6	57	Colombia	2,6
22	Ireland	28,2	58	Moldova	2,1
23	Cyprus	28,1	59	Korea, Rep.	2
24	Denmark	28,1	60	Ecuador	1,9
25	Canada	26,6	61	Armenia	1,8
26	Mali	25,3	62	El Salvador	1,6
27	Italy	24,2	63	Sri Lanka	1,6
28	Slovak Republic	22,5	64	China	1,5
29	New Zealand	22,1	65	Costa Rica	1,4
30	Mozambique	21,6	66	Thailand	1,2
31	Portugal	18,2	67	Kyrgyz Republic	0,8
32	Spain	17,7	68	Mexico	0,7
33	Ukraine	17,7	69	Mongolia	0,6
34	Singapore	16,7	70	Kazakhstan	0,5
35	Poland	16,1	71	Pakistan	0,5
36	Serbia	15	72	Philippines	0,5

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

References

Leogrande, A. (2024). Companies with at least 10 Employees Selling Online across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4785815.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Regular Internet Users Across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4782193.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Cultural and Creative Employment Across Italian Regions. Available at SSRN.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Knowledge Workers across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4772381.

Leogrande, A. (2024). The Propensity for Patenting in the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4771132.

Leogrande, A. (2024). The Innovation of the Production System in the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4771131.

Resta, E., Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Impact of Patent Applications on Technological Innovation in European Countries. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 28(3,), 1-15.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Innovation in European Countries in the period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(8), 91-126.

Costantiello, A., Leogrande, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The corporate innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 3964043.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-friendly environment in europe. Available at SSRN 3933553.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2020). The finance-innovation nexus in Europe. *IJISSET-International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology*, 7(12).

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The Impact of Venture Capital Expenditures on Innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 3930697.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., De Cristoforo, G., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Innovation-Sales Growth Nexus in Europe. Available at SSRN 3933407.

- Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A.(2020). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR), 4(11), 166-187.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. Available at SSRN 3983218.
- Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. Available at SSRN 4010098.
- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Matarrese, M. (2022). Innovative SMEs Collaborating with Others in Europe. Available at SSRN 4103840.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Marketing and Organizational Innovations in Europe. Available at SSRN 4186167.
- Angelo, L., Laureti, L., & Alberto, C. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.
- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Impact of New Doctorate Graduates on Innovation Systems in Europe. Available at SSRN 4209643.
- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Role of Non-R&D Expenditures in Promoting Innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 4215981.
- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The opportunity driven entrepreneurship in the context of innovation systems in Europe in the period 2010-2019. Available at SSRN 4229027.
- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The impact of patent applications on technological innovation in European countries. Available at SSRN 4275264.
- Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Impact of New Doctorate Graduates on Innovation Systems in Europe. International Journal of Entrepreneurship, 28(3,), 1-22.
- Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Opportunity Driven Entrepreneurship in the Context of Innovation Systems in Europe in the Period 2010-2019. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP, 28(3,), 1-13.